

AN ANALYSIS OF GENDER PERSPECTIVES IN VIRGINIA WOOLF’S “TO THE LIGHTHOUSE”

Umarova Marjona Usmonovna

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Abstract. *This article examines Virginia Woolf’s “To the Lighthouse” through a feminist lens, focusing on its portrayal of gender roles and the contrasting representations of femininity embodied by Mrs. Ramsay and Lily Briscoe. Mrs. Ramsay reflects the Victorian ideal of womanhood, devoted to domesticity and self-sacrifice, while Lily Briscoe represents the emerging modern woman, seeking artistic and intellectual independence. Woolf critiques patriarchal values by highlighting the limitations placed on women and exploring themes of personal and creative freedom. The study utilizes a close textual analysis, supported by Woolf’s feminist essays and biographical context, to reveal how the novel challenges traditional gender roles and advocates for female autonomy. This research contributes to a deeper understanding of Woolf’s feminist ideology and her subtle yet impactful critique of societal expectations for women.*

Keywords: *virginia woolf, To the Lighthouse, feminism, gender roles, patriarchy, victorian femininity, artistic independence, modernism*

Introduction

Virginia Woolf’s “To the Lighthouse” (1927) is a profound exploration of consciousness, memory, and human relationships. Its nuanced portrayal of gender, specifically the roles and identities of women within the framework of a patriarchal society, situates the novel as a significant feminist text. The novel’s two central female characters, Mrs. Ramsay and Lily Briscoe, provide contrasting models of womanhood: Mrs. Ramsay embodies traditional Victorian femininity, while Lily Briscoe represents the emerging modern woman, pursuing artistic and intellectual independence.

Woolf’s feminist ideology, though subtly woven into her narrative style, is powerfully expressed through these characters and their interactions with the male-dominated world they inhabit. By examining these characters, the novel’s treatment of patriarchal values, and Woolf’s own biographical context, this paper seeks to explore “To the Lighthouse” as a text that challenges traditional gender roles, advocating for female autonomy and creative expression.

Methods

This study employs a qualitative, interpretive approach based on textual analysis. The primary focus is a close reading of “To the Lighthouse”, concentrating on Woolf’s depiction of Mrs. Ramsay and Lily Briscoe. To support the analysis, secondary sources, including critical essays and feminist readings of Woolf’s work, were consulted. The research framework is grounded in feminist literary criticism, particularly the theories of Virginia Woolf herself as expressed in her essays such as “A Room of One’s Own” (1929). Woolf’s own life, especially her relationship with her parents and her views on gender, also plays a crucial role in interpreting the novel’s thematic content.

Results

Mrs. Ramsay, as a central figure in “To the Lighthouse”, epitomizes the Victorian notion of the “Angel in the House”—a woman whose value lies in her domesticity, nurturing abilities, and emotional caretaking (Hussey, 1995). She is revered by her family and guests for her ability to create harmony and stability within the home. However, Woolf presents Mrs. Ramsay not only as an idealized figure but also as one confined by societal expectations. Her internal reflections

reveal her ambivalence toward her role and moments of existential contemplation, which Woolf uses to subtly critique the limitations of this ideal (Goldman, 2006).

Woolf’s portrayal of Mrs. Ramsay reflects her own relationship with her mother, Julia Stephen, who similarly embodied the Victorian feminine ideal (Lee, 1996). Through Mrs. Ramsay, Woolf explores the tension between societal expectations and personal fulfillment. The eventual death of Mrs. Ramsay symbolizes the decline of the Victorian feminine ideal as modernist values emerge.

Lily Briscoe represents a new kind of woman—one not defined by her relationships with men or her role within the family. As an artist, Lily struggles with both societal expectations and her own doubts about her abilities. Male characters, such as Charles Tansley, reflect the sexist attitudes of the time, famously asserting that “women can’t paint, women can’t write” (Woolf, 1927, p. 86). Despite these external pressures, Lily persists in her artistic endeavors, and her completion of the painting at the novel’s end represents a triumph over the limitations imposed by patriarchal society (Marcus, 1981).

Lily’s artistic journey mirrors Woolf’s own experiences as a female writer in a male-dominated literary world (Silver, 1990). The completion of her painting is symbolic of creative autonomy, suggesting Woolf’s broader feminist message: that women’s intellectual and artistic contributions are valuable and should be recognized.

While Woolf does not directly attack patriarchy in “To the Lighthouse”, her critique is embedded in her depiction of male characters, particularly Mr. Ramsay. His preoccupation with his intellectual pursuits and his emotional dependency on Mrs. Ramsay highlights the self-centered nature of patriarchal expectations (Banfield, 2000). Mr. Ramsay’s philosophical endeavors contrast sharply with Mrs. Ramsay’s emotional labor, and Woolf uses this juxtaposition to critique the societal structures that devalue women’s work (Lee, 1996).

The novel’s modernist structure and its focus on interiority further serve Woolf’s feminist critique. By centering the narrative on the consciousness and emotional experiences of women, Woolf disrupts traditional narrative forms and challenges the patriarchal conventions of literary realism (Goldman, 2006).

Discussion

Virginia Woolf’s “To the Lighthouse” can be read as a feminist text that interrogates traditional gender roles. Through the contrasting figures of Mrs. Ramsay and Lily Briscoe, Woolf explores the limitations placed on women by a patriarchal society and the potential for female autonomy and creative expression. Mrs. Ramsay embodies the Victorian feminine ideal but is ultimately confined by it, while Lily Briscoe represents the possibility of a new, independent womanhood.

Woolf’s portrayal of these characters, along with her critique of male intellectualism as represented by Mr. Ramsay, reflects her broader concerns with the social and intellectual liberation of women. The novel’s modernist form, with its focus on subjectivity and interiority, serves as both a stylistic and thematic challenge to the patriarchal structures of Woolf’s time.

Conclusion

Virginia Woolf’s “To the Lighthouse” presents a powerful exploration of gender roles and the societal limitations placed on women. Through Mrs. Ramsay, Woolf critiques the Victorian ideal of womanhood, while Lily Briscoe’s journey reflects the possibilities for female artistic and intellectual freedom. The novel’s feminist themes, combined with its modernist narrative style, make it a seminal work in feminist literary criticism. Woolf’s subtle yet profound critique of

patriarchy continues to resonate, offering insights into the complexities of gender identity and the ongoing struggle for female autonomy.

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